

Determinants of Low Birth Weight among newborns delivered in the Selected Hospitals at Puducherry – A Case Control Study

P. Priyanka¹, Dr. Manjubala Dash², Dr. T. Nanthini³

¹M.Sc., Nursing-II-year, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecological Nursing, Mother Theresa Institute of Health Sciences, Puducherry, India.

²Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecological Nursing, MTPG&RIHS

³Professor, Department of Community Health Nursing, MTPG&RIHS

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Babies that are delivered prematurely or with inadequate prenatal growth, or both, are more likely to have low birth weights. Low birth weight infants can be addressed during the antenatal period. If their babies were handled properly, many mothers go on to lead very normal lives. **Aim of the study:** The main aim of the study the determinants of low birth weight babies among newborns and to estimate the magnitude of the determinants. **Methodology:** The research approach adopted for this study was Quantitative approach. Epidemiological – Case-control study research design was used to estimate the determinant factors for Low birth weight babies. The total sample size was 150 mothers and neonates. The samples were selected using Purposive sampling technique. **Results:** The study results shows that the mean score of age among postnatal mothers in the cases group was 25.78 +3.93, gestational age in weeks was 36.72 + 2.15 and BMI was 24.17 + 5.76 ,whereas in the control group ,the mean score of age among postnatal mothers was 26.11 + 3.88 , gestational age in weeks 38.31+1.42, and BMI was 25.25 + 4.67. There is a positive determinants in odds ratio shows, there is a significant risk of 3 times (OR=3.128) for the mothers with history of preterm delivery, there is a significant risk of 2 times (OR=2.250) of mothers with Hemoglobin level less than 11g/dl, and mother who had not consuming the Multivitamin there is a significant risk of 2 times (OR=2.042) to develop Low Birth Weight babies. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that determinants of Low Birth Weight babies was high in the hemoglobin level of mothers. Proper nutrition and health education in antenatal period helps the mother to prevent from Low Birth Weight babies

Keyword: Low birth weight, Newborn, case control study.

Introduction

Childbirth, also known as labor, parturition, and delivery, is the completion of pregnancy where one or more babies exist in the internal environment of the mother via vaginal delivery or cesarean section.¹

Low birth weight (LBW), which is defined as birth weight less than 2500 g, is a serious public health concern that is still a big problem in India.⁴ As one of the biggest risk factors for infant mortality and morbidity, low birth weight has emerged as the new worldwide public health problem.²

According to WHO guidelines, LBW has been used as an important health indicator of a public health issue because it reflects maternal malnutrition and metabolic conditions as well as inadequate prenatal care at the population level, making it the best predictor of newborn health and survival.³

Low birth weight infants can be addressed during the antenatal period. If their babies were handled properly, many mothers go on to lead very normal lives. Early intervention is crucial, especially for managing feeding, handling, sanitation, and infection control. The baby's health and nutritional status are reflected in the mother's understanding of infant care. Nurses play an important role in providing the mother of an LBW with dependable management techniques. Counselling provided to mothers of LBW babies by nurses may help the mother feel less stressed and work alongside the nurses to care for the baby.⁴

Need for the study

Babies who are born weighing less than 5 pounds, 8 ounces (2,500 grams) are referred to as having a low birth weight. An average infant typically weighs around 8 pounds. Despite being little, a baby with a low birth weight may nevertheless be healthy. However, a newborn with a low birth weight may potentially experience a variety of grave health issues.⁵ Babies that are born with LBW run the risk of developing a variety of health issues, such as hypothermia, hypoglycemia, cognitive decline, malnutrition, etc.⁶

The high frequency of LBW newborns can be attributed to a number of epidemiological factors, including maternal age, parity, and spacing time.⁷ Low birth weight is an important public health indicator of maternal health, healthcare delivery, nutrition, and poverty, and there is an inverse link between low

birth weight and socioeconomic status. Compared to newborns who are born weighing more than 2.5 kg, low birth weight infants have a 20 times higher risk of dying.⁸

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines low birth weight as weighing less than 2500 g at birth. Low birth weight is still a major global public health issue, and it has a variety of short- and long-term repercussions. More over 20 million babies a year, or 15% to 20% of all births worldwide, are thought to be low birth weight.⁹ More over 20 million births each year, or between 15 and 20% of all births worldwide, are thought to be due to low birth weight. Around 30 million LBW babies are born annually worldwide (or 23.4% of all births). Half of all LBW births occur in South- Central Asia, where 27% of infants are born weighing less than 2500 g, compared to sub-Saharan Africa, where the estimated LBW rate is 15%.¹⁰

A study on maternal factors causing low birth weight in newborns in tertiary care hospital Puducherry reveals the result of a total of 225 babies and their mothers was included in the study among 124 were males and 101 were females, 204 were term, and 21 were preterm. The mean age of the mothers was 22.52±3.33 years, the mean weight noted was 62.94±10.09 kg and the mean height was 160.1±7.15 cm.

Statement of the problem

A Case-control study to assess the determinants of Low Birth Weight among newborns delivered in the selected hospitals, at Puducherry.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the determinants of low birth weight babies among newborns.
2. To estimate the magnitude of the determinants.
3. To associate the various determinants of Low Birth weight Babies with selected demographic, obstetric variables, and maternal and nutritional determinants of mothers and newborns.

Assumption:

There are various factors associated for having low birth weight babies.

Delimitation:

The study is delimited to,

1. Rajiv Gandhi Government Women and Children Hospital, Puducherry.
2. Mothers with Low Birth Weight babies
3. Sample size is 150 mothers and neonate (cases 50 and controls 100)
4. Period of data collection is 4 weeks.

Methodology

The research approach adopted for this study was Quantitative research approach. Epidemiological – Case-control study research design was used to estimate the determinant factors for Low birth weight babies. The study was conducted in the postnatal ward, Postoperative ward, and post-operative annex at RGGW&CH, Puducherry. The total sample size was 150 mothers and neonates (2:1 ratio of control and cases). 100 term babies and 50 LBW babies were selected for the control and cases respectively. Purposive sampling technique were used to select the cases (50), and a simple random sampling technique were used to select the controls (100).

Data collection procedure

Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authorities from the ethical committee, RGGW&CH Medical Officer to conduct the study. Informed oral and written consent was obtained from the individual sample prior to the data collection and confidentiality was maintained.

In cases (mothers with low birth weight babies) 50 samples were selected as per inclusion criteria by using Purposive sampling technique. Samples were selected from the postnatal ward and make them comfortable. For each subject data was collected by using a self-structured questionnaire to assess demographic variables, obstetric and neonatal variables, and a self-structured checklist was used to assess the determinants of the LBW babies. The researcher explained the purpose of the study and data was collected to each subject by interview method. It took 10-15 mins for each subject to complete the questionnaire. Each day 2 cases were interviewed.

In controls (mother with normal birth weight babies) 100 samples were selected as per inclusion criteria by using Simple random sampling technique. Samples were selected from the postnatal ward and make them comfortable. For each subject data was collected by using a self-structured questionnaire to assess demographic variables, obstetric and neonatal variables, and a self-structured checklist was used to assess the determinants of the LBW babies. The researcher explained the purpose of the study and data was collected to each subject by interview

method. It took 10-15 mins for each subject to complete the questionnaire. Each day 4 samples were interviewed.

Each day 5-6 samples were interviewed and confidentiality was maintained for each sample. A total 150 samples were selected in the form of 1:2 (Cases and Controls respectively). The Researcher introduced herself and the samples were informed that they would have the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Samples were cooperated and reassured them to maintain confidentiality throughout the study. The same procedure was followed throughout the period of data collection.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study reveals demographic variables shows that, the majority 27 (54.0%) and 54 (54.0%) were in the age group of 23 – 27 among the cases and controls. There were 2 mothers of low birth weight babies > 32 years in the cases and 8 mothers of low birth weight babies among the control group belonging to the age group of > 32 years.

Regarding marital status, residence, and religion, the study revealed that 50 (100.0%) were the married women, 25 (50.0%) had their residence in the rural areas and 25 (50.0%) had their residence in the urban area, majority 48 (96.0%) were belongs to Hindu religion and only 2(4.0%) were belongs to the Muslim religion and none of them belongs to Christian among the cases, whereas 100 (100.0%) were the married women, majority 55 (55.0%) had their residence in the rural areas and 45 (45.0%) had the residence in the urban areas, most 94 (94.0%) belongs to Hindu religion, were 3 (3.0) belongs to the Muslim religion, only 3 (3.0%) belongs to Christian religion among the control.

Considering the Type of Family, Family Income, and Educational status of the mother 15(30.0%) belongs to a Nuclear family, the majority were as 35(70.0%) belongs to joint family, whereas 15(30.0) had monthly family income of Rs. < 5000 and 22 (44.0%) had monthly family income of Rs. 5000-10000, only 13 (26.0%) had the monthly income >15000, whereas 22(44.0%) had the primary school education, majority 28 (56.0%) had the Degree among the cases, whereas only 32 (32.0%) belongs to Nuclear family, majority 68 (68.0%) belongs to Joint family, only 33 (33.0) had the family income of Rs. < 5000, majority 45 (45.0) belongs to family

income of Rs. 5000- 10000, were as 22(22.0) had the monthly income >15000, only 34 (34.0%) had the primary school education, majority 66 (66.0 %) had the Degree among the control.

Comparing the Occupation of the mother, Occupation of father, and Distance of medical facility, only 6 (12.0%) were employed, the majority 44(88.0%) belongs to the housewife, the majority 41 (82.0) were private workers,6(12.0) were farmer only 3(6.0) was the government employee, majority 46 (92.0) had the medical facility Within 5 km, only 4(8.0%) had the medical facility beyond 5 km among the cases, whereas 15 (15.0%) belongs to employed mother, majority 85 (85.0%) were housewife, majority 79(79.0%).

The findings shows that there was a significant association with the gestational week, weight of the baby, weight of the placenta, and weight of the mother in kg at $p<0.001$, $p<0.01$. There was no significant association in the pregnancy status, parity, gravida height of the mother, MUAC, No. of antenatal visits, type of delivery, sex of baby, bad obstetrical history.

There was a significant association with the history of Cardiovascular disease, Diabetes Mellitus, and Hypertension at $p<0.05$ level. No statistically significant association was observed for history of preterm delivery, history of abortion, history of sexually transmitted disease, history of thyroid, placenta previa, and history of contraceptive use.

There was a significant association with hemoglobin level at $p<0.05$. No statistically significant association was observed for hard physical work, hyperemesis during pregnancy, vaginal infection during pregnancy, TT vaccine before or during the pregnancy, violence during pregnancy.

Table 1: Odds ratio of maternal determinants between cases and controls –Past obstetrical history. N = 150(50+100)

Maternal Determinants	Cases	Controls	Odds Ratio
History of preterm delivery			3.128
Yes	3	2	
No	47	98	
History of abortion			1.275
Yes	8	13	
No	42	87	
History of sexually transmitted disease			-
Yes	0	0	
No	50	100	
History of comorbid illness			-
Cardiovascular disease	2	0	
DM	6	9	
Hypertension	8	7	
Nil	34	84	
History of any pregnancy complications			-
Thyroid	6	14	
Placenta previa	2	2	
Nil	42	84	
History of contraceptive use			0.922
Yes	7	15	
No	43	85	

The above tables depicts that there is a significant risk of 3 times (OR=3.128) for the mothers with a history of preterm delivery to develop LBW babies, there is 1 time (OR=1.275) for the mothers with a history of abortion to develop LBW babies. The history of sexually transmitted disease does not show any significant risk.

Table 2: Odds ratio of maternal determinants between cases and controls –Present obstetrical history N = 150(50+100)

Maternal Determinants	Cases	Controls	Odds Ratio
Hard physical work			-
Yes	0	3	
No	50	97	
Hyperemesis during pregnancy			1.760
Yes	35	57	
No	15	43	
Haemoglobin Level			2.250
11 g/dl or more	30	40	
Less than 11 g/dl	20	60	
Vaginal infection during pregnancy			1.652
Yes	4	5	
No	46	95	
Alcohol consumption			-
Yes	-	-	
No	50	100	
Smoking habits			-
Yes	-	-	
No	50	100	
TT vaccine before or during the pregnancy			0.490
Yes	48	98	
No	2	2	
Violence during pregnancy, if violence means what type?			-
Physical violence or sexual violence	0	1	
No violence	50	97	
Others	0	2	

The above table shows that in women who had Hyperemesis during their pregnancy there is 1 time (OR=1.760) significant risk of developing LBW babies and in women with Hb level less than 11g/dl there is a significant risk of 2 times (OR=2.250) to develop LBW babies and women with vaginal infection during the pregnancy were at odds for developing LBW babies to mothers (OR=1.652). There is no significant in the Violence during the pregnancy, alcohol consumption, Smoking habits, hard physical work.

Table 3: Odds ratio of nutritional determinants between cases and controls**N = 150(50+100)**

Nutritional Determinants	Cases	Controls	Odds Ratio
Ate meat, bean, and green leafy vegetables			1.179
Yes	47	93	
No	3	7	
Multivitamin use			2.042
Yes	49	96	
No	1	4	
Iron and folic acid supplement for current pregnancy			1.000
Yes	47	94	
No	3	6	
Dietary counselling during the current pregnancy			1.325
Yes	17	28	
No	33	72	
Consuming extra meal during the current pregnancy			0.841
Yes	17	38	
No	33	62	
Eating out of home			1.120
Yes	12	22	
No	38	78	
Sometimes	-	-	
Food habits			1.213
Vegetarian	3	5	
Non-vegetarian	47	95	

The above table shows that women who had not taken the meat, bean, and green leafy vegetables there is 1 time (OR=1.179) significant risk of developing LBW babies, and women had not consuming the multivitamin there is a significant risk of 2 times (OR=2.042) to develop LBW babies and women were not received dietary counselling during the current pregnancy were at odds for developing LBW babies to mothers (OR=1.325), women had the habits of eating out of home were at odds for developing LBW babies to mothers (OR=1.

120), women had the habits of eating vegetarian food were at odds for developing LBW babies to mothers (OR=1. 213)

Table 4: Stepwise logistic regression model for independent risk factors for LBW
N = 150(50+100)

Variables	Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR) (95% CI)
Gestational week	
30 – 32	0.105 (0.005-2.21)
33 – 34	0.030 (0.002-.495)
35 – 36	0.02 (0.002-0.152)
≥37	1
Weight of the mother in kg	
<50 kg	0.21 (0.036-1.21)
≥50 kg	1
Weight of baby	
<2.5 kg	1
≥2.5 kg	0.00 (0.00)
Weight of placenta	
≥500 g	94.0 (12.85-687.2)
<500 g	1
History of comorbid illness	
Cardiovascular disease	0.00 (0.00-)
DM	0.395 (0.10-1.55)
Hypertension	0.528 (0.15-1.84)
Nil	1
Hemoglobin Level	
11 g/dl or more	1
Less than 11 g/dl	3.133 (1.36-7.20)

The above table 4.3.4 shows that, in bivariate analysis, hemoglobin level were significantly associated with LBW at 95% level of significance (p-value 0.5). Multivariable analysis was done by multiple logistic regression method, Haemoglobin Level (AOR=3.133, CI 1.36-7.20) was the determinants of LBW, found significantly associated in multivariate analysis.

Table 5: Mean and Standard deviation of age, Gestational age in weeks and BMI at 1st visit
N = 150(50+100)

Variables	Cases		Controls	
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D
Age	25.78	3.93	26.11	3.88
Gestational age in weeks	36.72	2.15	38.31	1.42
BMI	24.17	5.76	25.25	4.67

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that history of preterm delivery, history of abortion, low hemoglobin level, multivitamin use, hyperemesis, and eating out of the home during pregnancy are determinants of Low Birth Weight babies out of which Low hemoglobin level is the major determinants which leads to Low Birth Weight babies. Mothers are educated during pregnancy on the effect of anemia to reduce the Low Birth Weight babies. Necessary education must be given to pregnancy related educational programs where mothers would be educated on the effects of Low Birth Weight babies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Although this is a hospital based study; the results may not be applicable to the general population at large groups. There may be a further need to elaborate the study using the large population including more study subjects and socio- demographic parameters to establish better statistical correlation.
2. In future studies, it is necessary to provide effective interventions for the prevention of LBW are important to reduce neonatal complications and to promote the infants to be healthy and safe.
3. Similar studies can be done to assess the determinants of Low Birth Weight babies.

REFERENCE:

1. Childbirth. In: Wikipedia [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 Sep 14]. Available from: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Childbirth&oldid=1175316669>
2. Singh D, Manna S, Barik M, Rehman T, Kanungo S, Pati S. Prevalence and correlates of low birth weight in India: findings from national family health survey 5. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2023 Dec;23(1):1–13.
3. Jamshed S, Khan F, Begum A, Barkat Ali B, Akram Z, Ariff M. Frequency of Low Birth Weight and its Relationship With Maternal Nutritional and Dietary Factors: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Cureus*. 12(6):e8731.
4. Ms.Rajwinder Kaur MsRK. Staff Nurses (Nicu) Knowledge Regarding Care Of Low Birth Weight Baby. *IOSR-JNHS*. 2013;1(3):1–4.
5. default - Stanford Medicine Children's Health [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 16]. Available from: <https://www.stanfordchildrens.org/en/topic/default?id=low-birthweight-90-P02382>
6. Shaohua Y, Bin Z, Mei L, Jingfei Z, Pingping Q, Yanping H, et al. Maternal risk factors and neonatal outcomes associated with low birth weight. *Frontiers in Genetics* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2023 Oct 18];13. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fgene.2022.1019321>
7. RAMAN TR, DEVGAN A, SOOD S, GUPTA A, RAVICHANDER B. LOW BIRTH WEIGHT BABIES : INCIDENCE AND RISK FACTORS. *Med J Armed Forces India*. 1998 Jul;54(3):191–5.
8. Singh G. Low Birth Weight: Prevalence and Risk Factors. *JGWH*. 2020 Aug 24;19(4):43–50.
9. Global nutrition targets 2025: low birth weight policy brief [Internet]. [cited 2023 Aug 14]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/WHO-NMH-NHD-14.5>

10. Tadesse T, Abebe M, Molla W, Ahmed Mahamed A, Mebratu A. Magnitude and associated factors of low birth weight among term newborns delivered in Addis Ababa public hospitals, Ethiopia, 2021. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2023 Dec 31;43(1):2114332.
11. Das S, Mollick SA, Ray S. Consequences of Low Birth Weight among Tribal Populations in India: A Review Analysis. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2022 Sep 8;12(9):108–16.
12. Mallick A. Prevalence of low birth weight in India and its determinants: Insights from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS), 2015–2016. *Anthropologischer Anzeiger*. 2021 Jan 8;78.
13. Sharma N, Sharma P, Wavare RR, Sharma P, Sharma N. An insight into the prevalence of low birth weight in Madhya Pradesh. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics*. 2021 May 25;8(6):1091–5.
14. Roy A, Akter ZM, Biswas DC. Trends in prevalence of low-birth-weight babies in India. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics*. 2021 Sep 23;8(10):1725–9.
15. Khan N, Mozumdar A, Kaur S. Determinants of low birth weight in India: An investigation from the National Family Health Survey. *Am J Hum Biol*. 2020 May;32(3):e23355.
16. Kumar M, Verma R, Khanna P, Bhalla K, Kumar R, Dhaka R, et al. Prevalence and associate factors of low birth weight in North Indian babies: a rural based study. *International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health*. 2017 Aug 23;4(9):3212–7.